

ABUDoF

**JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES, DEPARTMENT OF
FRENCH,**

AHMA

DU

BELLO UNIVERSITY,

ZARIA - NIGERIA

ISSN 1595-7004

Vol. 1, No 7, September 2008

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Overseas Subscribers

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EDITORIAL POLICY

ABUDoF, a Journal of the Department of French, Ahmadu Bel, I University is committed to the promotion of research in the Humanities. This implies that it accepts articles in any area of the Humanities but with emphasis on French which is its primary area of concern.

The Journal is published annually in September. Acceptance of articles runs through the year and could be on any area of French Studies.

However, for the forthcoming edition, Vol. 1 No 8, emphasis will be on fresh issues in Linguistics studies and teaching, Francophone Poetry and Drama and contemporary issues in French and Francophone Politics. If articles based on the novel are to be submitted, they must be works published not earlier than 2000.

The recommended mode of presentation is MLA (inter-text) or APA. Contributors are strongly advised to acquaint themselves with these modes which do not admit foot or endnotes; only bibliography is required as articles that fail to conform to either of these will be rejected outrightly. Font is 12.

Assessment fee for each article submitted is N2, 000 while the author of an accepted article will contribute N8, 000 towards the publication of the Number.

All articles to be considered for publication in Vol. 1 No 8 of ABUDoF should reach the Editor not later than June 2009. Articles submitted after this date will be considered for publication only in the following issue of ABUDoF.

All articles should be sent in electronic form and copy to:

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EDITORIAL

ABUDoF, Ahmadu Bello University Journal of Humanities is out again. The slumber has been long but not without reasons. A major cause was the problem of obtaining enough quality articles that met, in content and form, the standard of ABUDoF. Quite a number of the articles received by the Editor, where they met the Journal's standard in content, were deficient in the manner of their presentation. To ABUDoF, just as to any journal worthy of the name, the profoundness of the thematic freight is as important as the form. In the face of this manifest inadequacy attested to, moreover, by our assessors, ABUDoF had to sift and wait.

The articles appearing in this Volume reflect efforts by the contributors to sensitize the ABUDoF readership to fresh issues in their individual areas of specialization. The articles provide new grounds for rethinking some of our positions on the issues raised by the authors.

There is a striking lack of articles on Poetry and paucity of articles on Francophone Theatre in this Number. This limitation is not peculiar to ABUDoF but rather a common development in Francophone African scholarship. These once ebullient areas should not be allowed to pale out. ABUDoF therefore invites contributors to its future Numbers to assist in the restoration of these genres that were once the pride of Francophone Negro African Literature. We should, of course, also keep alive researches into the three genres of Metropolitan French Literature which are obviously suffering from neglect at our time.

This Volume of ABUDoF is being published at a time of deep grief to the Department of French. Prof B.F. Alisah who was for a long time the Editor of the Journal and a source of inspiration to us died after a protracted illness in Ghana. Prof Alisah's sudden departure also contributed to the delay in publishing this Number of ABUDoF. We pray for the repose of his soul.

We thank our contributors for their confidence in ABUDoF. We are particularly grateful to our assessors who had to create the time out of their tight schedules to assess our articles.

We welcome suggestions towards improving the standard of ABUDoF.

Prof R.A. Adebisi
Editor
September 2008

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PEDAGOGY

GLOBALISATION AND THE CHALLENGES OF SUSTAINABLE READING CULTURE: THE RELEVANCE OF EFFECTIVE PLAYWRITING

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Abstract

The art of writing and reading are facing the most pronounced challenges in human history, occasioned by the availability of several options through the current high information technology-globalization. Reading, either for formal or leisure purposes, is in stiff competition with entertainment and information alternatives available on the Internet. This paper argues that playwriting as an act, when properly handled, can create and sustain the reading culture of its audience, the said challenges notwithstanding.

Introduction

We live in a world today that has been unquestionably termed a global village. A period in world history that the socio - economic, political and even cultural activities of the entire mankind are, to a very large extent determined by the flow of high information technology coined globalization. Technology has invaded the essence of human existence right into the privacy of individual lives. Arguably, as positive as this development may be no doubt, like every human endeavour, globalization is also bedeviled with a lot of challenges and shortcomings. Amongst other aspects, through high information technology the owners and manipulators of this technology use this breakthrough principally for the global advancement and promotion of their economy and culture. This way, the underdeveloped economies of the world, who because of their economic incapability do not have what it takes to compete favourably with the developed economies, have found themselves once again in the world economic growth as mere consumers of the products of globalization rather than producers or even co-producers.

Because of this technological magic, a lot of contacts and access to information have become convenient more than ever before. But this portends a lot of danger for quiet a number of aspects of human relationship and societal regulations. With almost free access to the Internet, affordable access to all forms of entertainment on the Net, the art and craft of play writing and reading are faced with the greatest challenge in world history. How do you convince a person to sit down and create or read a play work when he has several

alternatives that are by far, comparatively more convenient for him to benefit than the pains of creating? Creating works for who to read?

However, in spite of this alternative entertainment value to playwriting and reading, this article is of the understanding and acceptability of the fact that the global threats from globalization notwithstanding, playwriting and reading have their place(s) that the weight of high information technology cannot submerge. The playwright and reader of the work are themselves products of the society and their readiness to blend in-between these two extremes, add spice to life long and sustainable reading culture.

The playwright

The playwright is the person who accepts the challenge, and practices playwriting. Amongst other characteristics, he is, according to Emman Dandaura in (Illah, 2002:100) the one who,

...observes current happenings in his society, which he then reflects and analyses in his work with a view to predict future happenings. His aim being to raise the consciousness of his people to the basic contradictions inherent in their society, so as to launch the society, into the future as a better developed, progressive and self-informed community. This way, the playwright functions as a historian, social commentator and visionary in his society. Since these tripartite roles of the playwright as artist, seer and social commentator are fused together, the playwright functions better as a nation builder only if, as Achebe opines, he demonstrates “a proper sense of history” so that he can correctly tell his fellow citizens where they went wrong, and where the rain began to beat them.

It is fundamental for the playwright to be aware of his responsibilities, both to himself, his work and the society. Not only should a play be readable, it must be good work of art. There are many ways of identifying good writing from its opposite. One way to distinguish the real from the fake play is what (Stolnitz, 1965:45) tags “the infectiousness of writing”. He contends and appropriately too, that the recipient of a truly artistic impression should be so united to the creative work that he feels as if the work were his own and not someone else’s. There can hardly be this infectiousness without the clarity of message(s) in the play. No one can adequately respond to instructions, if such instructions are hazy and clumsy.

Idegu in (Aliyu,2004:191) contends that the playwright must be sincere with his feelings, in fact; he should be impelled by an inner need to express his feelings as he experienced it either in real life situations or as created by him. It is sincerity, propelled by inner feelings and conviction that eases his writing as he is impelled to find clear expression for the feeling which he wishes to pass across. When the play does not transmit the writer's peculiarity of feeling, when it is unintelligibly expressed or when it has not proceeded from the writer's inner need for expression, obviously, reading such a work will not be meaningful because the work itself is far from a good play. This accounts for unavoidable poor readership when the play is badly handled. Yet as a playwright, it will be the greatest disservice to shy away from pursuing good creative exercise.

To successfully create a work that attracts good readership, the playwright must remember that, there is the "what" and the "how" in the process of perceptive growth. What he feels, thinks, believes in, loves, fears and hopes for, serves his impetus, and how he has chosen to express his idea in terms of the corrections determines whether he is a good playwright or not. (Yerima,2003:71). The issues of the need for the playwright to handle his work well can hardly be overflogged. Good and comprehensible reading starts from how adequately appropriate the content of the play process is. This is why (Yerima,2003:71) asserts again that the playwright must learn that,

...a narrow ideological outlook has a negative effect on the work and its readership. It leads the writer to what Soyinka calls an "unproductive" level. It is important to know that, if, an idea is to be well developed it must go through the process of thought. It is not enough for the playwright to say "I want to write about such and such" without first zeroing in on what "such and such" entails, and how well it will fit in with the chosen structure of the plot and the form.

This way, the play process will flow and make reading highly productive.

Sometimes, it is the name of the playwright that first attracts the reader. This is why Idegu in (Aliyu, 2004:102) advises that from a sample of their works, writers should be easily identified either because of their style in the use of language, ideological perception or mode and genre of presentation. Ola Rotimi was easily known for his simplicity in the use of English language so much that he was observed to be using "Yorubanglish", a coinage of Yoruba and English as a vibrant meeting point of these two complex languages. J. P. Clark is known as a playwright who, at the expense of dramatic dialogue, sacrifices his poetic beauty. Femi Osofisan is recognized for his revolutionary

theatre aesthetics. Achebe is the master story teller who uses proverbs so well because to him “proverb is the palm oil with which words are eaten”. Wole Soyinka’s works are mostly drawn from Yoruba myths. When a writer is able, over a period of time to carve such a niche for himself, it makes reading, especially when it is leisure reading, less cumbersome for his already captured reading audience.

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Strategies for Promoting Playwriting and Sustainable **Reading Culture**

It is not just enough for the playwright to know who he is and his responsibility to the society which influences him and which he in turn influences. It is imperative for him to have a firm grasp of certain elements that encourage readership and also sustain the reading culture. These include;

a. Playwriting for Formal Reading, For play writing to meet its purpose, the writer should know that every target audience, to a certain extent, determines the content and style of writing. When it comes to writing for formal reading, or writing a text for academic use, a lot of issues are considered. It is true that most literates, especially youths, will not read some texts except when they are recommended for their formal school training. Even at that, experience over the years prove that the content, volume and amongst others, good use of English language in such texts are considered by the readership. Writers must understand that, as Daudu in (Aliyu,2000:5), attests, reading is acknowledged as basic skill for information seeking and life - long education. Therefore, it is only when people can read well that they can acquire this basic skill. Because of the academic demands of students, especially at the tertiary level, and the several distractions, it is always advisable that play texts written for this purpose should as much as possible not be too voluminous. The volume of any play text has a lot to do with the interest in reading it especially when such reading is not for leisure but first, for academic purposes.

Literary texts encourage extensive reading because it stimulates the thinking process which is an essential need for the promotion of development - oriented citizenry. The school is a formal training ground for future leaders of any nation. How well they read will aid their understanding of challenges they face now and much later in life. This is why life - long literacy is very relevant for thinking creatively, making decisions, solving developmental - based problems, seeing things with the inner eye, applying facts to reality and reasoning productivity. (Jatau in Aliyu, 2004:32) The reading of literary texts will greatly enhance these factors. How much of literary texts are read remains a vital way of measuring literacy level; that is what is read, how what is read is understood, the use which what is read is put, and how often one reads. Thus, a really literate person or a literate society is that individual or society whose

greater majority of citizens can read “beyond the lines”. Literacy should not stop at being able to read, write, numerate and process documents, rather literacy should include the ability to make use of reading, writing, and manipulating skills for meaningful and productive living. (Gabriel (et al) in Aliyu,2000:54) The place that is most vibrant to realize this breakthrough in literacy is writing literacy texts for formal reading. It is in the realization of this vibrancy that universities all over Nigeria today have General Studies Departments where courses like English for Academic Purposes, English and Communication Skills and the like, are taught. Playtexts are most often also recommended for reading and assessment in these courses, thereby “forcing” students to read works that ordinarily, if they were to choose, they will not read. This “forceful” reading assists most students to discover in the course of their training, the benefits in not only reading, but having their reading culture sustained.

b. Playwriting for Leisure Reading. Unlike playwriting as literacy text where readers are “forced” to read for acquisition of academic certificates, leisure reading is principally, a matter of choice. In these days that the globe is flooded with multiplicity of recreations and leisure, playwriting nonetheless, still has its place. Like playwriting for formal reading, reading for pleasure also enhances life-long personality development because the information one acquires through reading enriches one’s perspective and broadens one’s understanding of the people, events and things around him. It acquaints one with new concepts, new points of view, and current approaches to issues and new solutions to existing problems. (Muodumogu (et al) in Aliyu,2004:65) But in spite of this great importance of reading for pleasure, there is the strong indication that a great number of people do not read as they ought to.

Several reasons are responsible for low readership of playtexts for leisure. Because the leisure reader is not under any compulsion (as one may assume with the literacy text reading), if the playtext is not interesting and attention-catching, its sustainable reading level will be very low. It is therefore expected that for play writing to sustain reading culture, it should have serious appeal in its packaging (quality of print), content, form and genre to the reader. In addition to these, one other way to encourage people to read is by making interesting reading materials not only easily available but affordable.

Iji, in (Okwori, 2004:12) compares the Nigerian experience with the West when he concludes that unquestionably, the western world at governmental, corporate or capable individual levels do consistently sponsor or support the varied disciplines of the creative arts due to their deep and sustained appreciation of the roles of play writing in nation - building through direct and indirect enlistments of the moral, spiritual, mental and material well beings of

humanity. African governments, corporate bodies and individuals should come up to sponsor playwrights in achieving the enviable role of sustaining 'reading culture of the literate society.

c. Topicality and Universality of Thematic Thrust. Every society of the world has issues that are immediate, identifiable and form part of their history, culture, tradition and the entire essence of their being. One way therefore, for the playwright to promote reading culture of a people, is to treat issues that they can see in their daily life experiences; issues about their past that they still refer to with contagious nostalgia, heroes they adore, deify and in some extreme instances, worship; issues that remind them of their roots, where they originated and the journey to where they are now and hope to go. Nevertheless, while the playwright is engaged in satisfying the immediate need of his target audience, he must not forget to also reflect on issues that are universal. But before such universalities are highlighted, the people must be exposed to their own feelings and life in the play, from which they can comparably comprehend the issues that though global, they can identify with their own immediate socio - cultural milieu.

Poverty, for instance, is universal. The poor person on the streets of Lagos is daily facing the same social malady like his counterparts on the streets of New York. Poverty has no respect of age, gender, race and even geographical configurations. However, it is always better to start from the known to the unknown. The northern Nigerian reader would most probably have understood the Toma and Tani primary school Reader far better, if these alien characters were first understood by the readers by the treatments of their own familiar names Ibrahim and Ladi that they have, feel, see and relate with everyday better. This assessment is the same for stories and poems with the regular phrase, "whiter than snow" for us in this part of the world where there is no snowfall. "Whiter than wool" sounds more topical and easily understandable for us, and thereafter woofs similarity with snow on colour (not texture) level could be explored.

When topical issues are treated in playwriting and thereafter, universal themes are injected into the reading culture, it builds a bridge between the immediate and remote social peculiarities of mankind. The African playwright constantly draws his materials and inspirations from what (Dasyuva,2001:1 19) calls African philosophical hermeneutics and loric tradition. He goes further to opine that, at the same time since he is exposed to western education, more often than not, the contemporary African usually benefits from the influences of the western play forms and traditions. This dual exposure of the African playwright with the topical and universal, contribute to the rich and unique

hybrid form (African and European) of what we can term modern African playwriting.

It is because of this hybridization that the concept and practice of, for example, feminism, is being constantly challenged in Nigerian and African play texts. William, citing Acholonu in (Adediran, 2002:41) observes on this universal matter of feminism that

The African cultural challenge was necessitated by the need to de-conceptualize the Eurocentric basis of feminism theory. In its conceptually perceived form, African cultural epistemologies stem from the need to de-mystify the perceived European cultural category of epistemologies as the universal standards in gender constructs. Since gender roles vary between cultures and different societies, then a projection of western paradigm as the universal experiences of women will sound practically unreasonable. The western theory of feminism is presumed to be based on the idea of the inequality of the sexes which places men and women on one side of the pedestal, with women struggling to depose the men and to look like, behave like and live like men.

Reading a play text on feminism from the Nigerian/African perspective will not only expose our indigenous value systems for women over and above the universal paradigm, but it will also sustain reading culture as some sense of patriotism is evoked in the reader who reads his or her own true life experience presented as it ought to be by one of them. In line with the above Foluso in (Aliyu, 2004:9), supports the view that reading provides a back-up of information which reduces ignorance, thus empowering and promoting literacy and communication.

There is the need to also note that the choice of an ideological focus of the playwright notwithstanding, some times the difference in the sex of who does the writing matters. Jatau in (Aliyu, 2004:29), asserts that,

A lot of creative works written by men did not reflect the trials and tribulations of child bearing and rearing, a central experience of the woman, instead, they reflect on male views of reality or reinforce male views of women in presenting stereotypical female characters and experiences. Male representations of women in their (male) creative works are usually one-sided.

Jatau in (Aliyu,2004:32) therefore submits that life-long women reading and literacy can be enhanced through play writing especially where women are motivated by a fair representation of their own experience in the texts they read. Hausa women in northern Nigeria, Jatau observes, for instance, are criticized for their increasing love for *soyoya* books from Hausa popular culture particularly the Kano market literature. These works bear very close thematic and plot arrangements with Indian movies, nevertheless because the works correspond with their everyday life, fashion, beauty, love and romance, they receive great acceptability in readership. However, while criticism on these books continue to rage, this has not discouraged the readership and reading culture cultivated by these women rather it has served to reinforce it through adult education. This has gone a long way in increasing the level of literacy in the low literate northern part of Nigeria. All the playwrights need to do now is to gradually and fully domesticate or topicalise the stories in the Kano market literature.

d, **Use of Language.** The effective use of language plays a prominent role in the understanding of the content of any play text. Though the official language of communication in Nigeria is English language, the manipulation and embellishment of English language by the playwright and its extent of success determine how receptive his work will be to the readers. There is for instance, a level of which indigenous culture values like proverbs, parables and anecdotes and how they are implored in a play, ease the understanding of the work. Even when the cultural aesthetics are absent the simplicity of English language usage has its place. When a playwright creates, he should have an audience in mind. It is not the depth of language usage for tertiary institutions and graduates that should be used for pupils in primary schools because even within the literate audience, the levels of their understanding of English as the language of communication vary. Any play which the reader ends up reading the dictionary more than the playtext to comprehend the play will never, most probably, make any desired impact on the reader. This does not however, advocate watering down English language usage as this will also be counterproductive.

On the place of language in play writing and suitability of reading, Ola Rotimi's response on the issue of the use of English language will suffice. Rotimi asserts,

English as you know is the official medium of communication in Nigeria. Inevitably, I write for audiences who are knowledgeable in this language. However, in handling the English language in my plays, I strive to temper

its phraseology to the ear of both the dominant semi - literate as well as the literate classes, ensuring that my dialogue reaches out to both groups with ease in assimilation and clarity in identification. (Ogunbiyi, 1981:39)

The primary job of the playwright therefore, includes amongst others, having the literate and semi - literate reading culture of his audience at heart while writing. At the end of the exercise, the hallmark of a successful creative work is to “reach to the audience with ease in assimilation and clarity in identification”. The reader should be able to, through good English language usage, identify the story, the characters, the setting, the conflict and all other elements in the play text. But not all playwrights are as considerate as Ola Rotimi. When asked a similar question of his style of writing and the perception or reception by his readers, Wole Soyinka opines,

Quite frankly, I write in the firm belief that there must be a least a hall full of people who are sort of on the same wavelength as mine from every stratum of society and there must be at least a thousand people who are able to feel the same way as I do about something. (Ogunbiyi, 1981:39)

Except the early plays of Soyinka like, *The Lion and the Jewel*, and *The Jero plays* (The Trials of Brother Jero and Jero’s metamorphosis) that can fit into his assertion here, the majority of his works were written with no particular audience in mind and no consideration for the semi - literal audience. When a writer creates a work of art and assumes that the readers should be of “the same wave-length “ with him, he will have select and limited readership. This explains the popularity of Rotimi’s plays from the secondary to tertiary education levels over and above Soyinka’s. The instance where the reader needs an interpreter to interpret Soyinka’s novel, *The Interpreters* to him, is highly problematic to the cordiality of relationship that ought to exist between the creative writer and the reader. When this occurs, reading and sustainable reading culture is negatively affected.

e. The Use of a People’s Culture. Simply put, culture is a people’s way of life; how they behave, live, dress, marry and how they also choose to relate with others. For reading to be encouraged and sustained playwrights should in their work, project and promote the culture of the people about whom they write. A lot of criticisms have followed the overbearing influence of foreign cultures on the early plays in this Nigeria. This notwithstanding, a lot of writers, within this same period, also made their marks with the way indigenous cultures of their people were reported.

It is not in doubt that the contact with colonial masters and foreign cultures has subverted and still inverts our cultural essence. These anomalies can be checked if playwrights continue to define and re-define our culture as we really are and want to be seen, not as the foreign writers hitherto, portrayed us. Government, at all levels, may not even be helping matters when this aspect of cultural promotion is mentioned. This is why Iji, citing Yaro Gella in (Okwori, 2004:12) records that

Culture has not been accorded a significant place in the national planning strategy of this country. That self-reliance, self-sufficiency and national identity as the core areas of our national development objectives hinge on the recognition of culture as the springboard of policies has hardly dawned on our policy makers.

With this kind of government response to cultural promotion, the role of play writing in sustaining reading culture in Nigeria, as one may argue for Africa becomes crucial. Culture is not static, it is dynamic. Playwrights should therefore move with this dynamism in cultural issues they choose to highlight to an immediate or remote target audience or both. Although culture is dynamic, it nevertheless remains essentially conservative. Gowon agrees that,

Culture is transmitted from one generation to another and it is this transmission that has direct bearing and latitude with playwriting. The nexus between culture and playwriting and reading culture is largely transformational. While culture generates codes on which a people's behavioural pattern is anchored, creative writing provides the vehicle with which these codes are passed from one generation to another.

Creativity and culture interplay at various levels to produce for the reader and or audience, a picture of the casual complexes that characterize a society. (Okwori, 2004:143)

It is the accepted task of the playwright to make available to the reader of his work the culture of the people, its changing status and how, even with the dynamism of culture, some aspects can be retained and strengthened. By so doing the playwright can right several wrongs done to the people's culture. (Billington, 1991:67), reasoning along the same line documents that during the colonial experience,

Textbooks were those produced by the publishing houses of ' the imperial power. Education, then, with its promise of entry into the colonial, if not imperial elite, was not a process of the acquisition of neutral knowledge but include the assimilation of the culture values of the imperial power. The 'best' novels, plays, and paintings produced in any colonial society will be those which most successfully emulate the characteristics of cultural products already within the canon of the dominant high culture. Indigenous materials may be used as a source, but it underwent a transmutation fitted to the rules of western aesthetics before it because art rather than native 'craft'

Africa's decolonization notwithstanding, the relics and vestiges of colonial plays need to be seriously checkmated and replaced with playtexts that project us. African nations have diplomatic relations with so many countries. World over, cultural links between countries is a powerful weapon in bilateral relations. In recognition of this, most developed countries have cultural institutions whose objectives are to propagate their home culture in other countries of their diplomatic and political interests. But as Bakare in (Okwori, 2002:43) articulates,

Just like every institution must have an agenda, these institutions have an agenda to sell their own countries through culture in their host countries. However, if they observe that the host country operates from a weak standpoint, they then aspire for a 'forceful' assimilation of their own culture by the host country.

For our culture to remain relevant, the symbolic relationship between the playwright and the reader must be continuously strengthened through works that are very rich in the people's culture and are also affordable and readable.

f. The Use of Identifiable Characters. Characters are vehicles or personalities through whom messages in a play are delivered. It is important for the playwright to present characters that can attract and retain the reader's interest. Since he sets out to write for an audience, he must be aware that his characters should be familiar social types which emerge from his society so that both the readers and the larger audience can identify the live characters in their daily life experiences and thereafter, relate to them. Through character recognition, audiences use characters in plays to break through whatever

barriers of language or theme the play may present in order to achieve a full apprehension of the work.

When characters in any play, apart from achieving artistic effects, are as close to life as possible to the reader, a lot of artistic emotional relationship is established. This kind of relationship influences the reader in handling such creative situations when they occur in real life. That is why the reader for example, sympathizes with Odewale in Ola Rotimi's *Blame*, dislikes Odibei in Zulu Sofola's *Wedlock of the Gods*, understands the plight of the Elesin who must die, but wishes to live to enjoy life in Wole Soyinka's *Death and the King's Horseman*, because throughout the works, the reader is in close contact with a human pattern he identifies, that is close to him in his neighbourhood and he can easily associate with. Yerima (2003:92).

While creating these identifiable characters, playwrights should be wary of creating their heroes after their image and likeness reflective of their personal ideological stance which may not even go well with the readers. Stephen in (Adediran, 2002:58), documents that although by social status, African writers, as intellectuals belong to the elite class, by ideological conceptions a majority of the writers identify with the downtrodden. This ambivalence creates heroes who being the authorial mouthpiece of the gap between the ideal and reality and the need to bridge it, is an obsession to the writer and to his hero. This often leads the writers to create characters who will revolt against members of the upper class who constitute themselves into nuisance. This is common with revolutionary writers who, through their works, call for revolution of the masses against the status quo while the writers themselves remain in the ivory towers enjoying their academic freedom. Such play writings can cause reading indigestion and discourage good readership.

Conclusion

An attempt has been made in this paper to acknowledge the challenges inherent in playwriting and the need to encourage reading and sustaining the reading culture of the literate class. As demanding as these challenges are, and especially within the constructs of globalization, if the playwright is committed to his calling, the relevance of his work in a technologically diversified society like ours, will remain valid. The playwright responds with his total personality to a social environment which changes all the time. Being a sensitive creative artist, the playwright registers, with varying degrees of accuracy and success, the conflicts and tensions in his changing society (Idegu in Aliyu 2004:158).

This accounts for why the same writer can produce different types of work, sometimes parallel in mood, sentiments and the degree of optimism for after all, the writer himself lives in, and is shaped by history. In the midst of

the permanence of change, the playwright should still be easily identified with an ideological spine in his works. He should also always bear in his real and artistic minds that if his work is not readable he would have failed in his responsibility as an artist, a visionary and nation - builder. Finally, to make reading worthwhile, the playwright ought to accept the current difficulties and challenges he faces from super high information technology as unavoidable confrontations that he can nevertheless, surmount and use to his advantage in promoting and sustaining the reading culture of the people.

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